

Highlights

Reverse Osmosis Desalination for Greenhouse Irrigation: Experimental Characterization and Economic Evaluation Based on Energy Hubs

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- The combination of RO with greenhouse environments is studied.
- The economic model based on energy hub methodology ensures precise cost assessment.
- RO investment in greenhouse is recovered in under three years, promoting adoption.
- Using PV-RO systems does not significantly disrupt cash flow dynamics.

Reverse Osmosis Desalination for Greenhouse Irrigation: Experimental Characterization and Economic Evaluation Based on Energy Hubs

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Abstract

Water scarcity is a threat to crucial economic sectors, notably agriculture, which is a major concern in arid regions like Spain's Almería province, home to a substantial greenhouse industry. One of the possible solution for this fact is the use of alternative water sources, as desalination. This work offers a comprehensive characterization and economic evaluation of reverse osmosis desalinated water for greenhouse irrigation, exploring various scenarios, including photovoltaic electricity generation. To accomplish this, an economic model based on the energy hub methodology is proposed. This model provides a versatile framework that accounts for factors like variable electricity generation and water demand, allowing for accurate cost assessments. The results show that levelized cost of water between 2.51 and 3.69 €/m³ can be reached depending on the configuration of the system. Moreover, the cash flow analysis demonstrates that the investment in reverse osmosis systems for greenhouse irrigation can be recovered in less than three years in all the studied scenarios. These findings suggest that using reverse osmosis systems for greenhouse irrigation is a viable option particularly appealing to farmers and small associations in specific districts, promoting distributed desalination adoption in agriculture environments.

Keywords: Agriculture, Economic analysis, Solar desalination, Modelling, Optimal management

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1. Introduction

Water scarcity has gained critical significance in human development, emerging as a central subject of study for various national and international agencies, programs, and organizations (Dalampira and Nastis, 2020). This scarcity is not merely viewed from a hydrological perspective but also as a socio-economic phenomenon, as it can exert a substantial impact on vital economic activities such as agriculture. In fact, the agriculture industry stands as the primary global water consumer, accounting for approximately 70% of total consumption (with regional variations influenced by economic development and climatic conditions) (Aquastat, 2023). However, this percentage is anticipated to rise in tandem with the expansion of irrigated crop areas, currently trending at an annual increase of 1.3% (Velasco-Muñoz et al., 2018). This escalating water demand poses a significant threat to the sustainability of agriculture in arid or semi-arid regions, such as the Mediterranean basin, where many economies are heavily reliant on this sector.

The above-mentioned problem is the case of Almería province, which is situated in the southeastern part of Spain, and is characterized by a semi-arid climate and a pronounced water scarcity issue. Despite these challenges, agriculture plays a pivotal role in the economy of this arid region (De Rafael and Fernández-Prados, 2018). The province of Almería hosts the world's largest concentration of greenhouses, encompassing over 32000 ha of horticultural structures that yield more than 3.4 million tons of produce. The auxiliary industry generates €1.3 billion and provides employment to 5500 individuals (Cajamar, 2022). Therefore, to sustain this sector at its current level of development, the utilization of sustainable and alternative freshwater sources is required.

In this context, one of the most promising alternative sources to meet the escalating water demand of agriculture is desalination (Burn et al., 2015; Hipólito-Valencia et al., 2021). Among the different desalination techniques, Reverse Osmosis (RO) stands as the most frequently utilized and commercially widespread desalination technology, primarily attributed to its cost competitiveness relative to alternative desalination methods (Martínez-Álvarez et al., 2016; Amy et al., 2017). In fact, Spain is the leader in using RO desalinated water for agricultural purposes (Martínez-Álvarez et al., 2017). However, the use of this technology for irrigation is not only limited to Spain,

but is also being evaluated for different locations and types of crops, such as the cultivation of Pistachio in Iran (Rahimi et al., 2021), or other crops in Kuwait (Burn et al., 2015) and Israel (Caldera and Breyer, 2019).

Focusing on the case of Spain, and, particularly, in the south-eastern Spain, the prevailing approach involves large centralized desalination plants that supply water to various distributed irrigation communities following general production policies. This is the case of the the Carboneras desalination facility, boasting a capacity of 120000 m³/day, or the Campo Cartagena one, which provides 145000 m³/day of freshwater (Beltrán and Koo-Oshima, 2006). However, this model has notable drawbacks, including cost overruns in desalinated water production, which poses a major obstacle to the effective utilization of desalinated water in agriculture within the specific target region (Aznar-Sánchez et al., 2021). These costs are not only due to the high energy requirements of desalination systems (Martínez-Álvarez et al., 2018), but also to the lack of particularization of this centralized approach, where all crops are treated equally without taking into account the specific needs of each one, which has been recently pointed out as one of the main gaps in the current state of the development of the technology for this particular region (Martínez-Álvarez et al., 2023).

Regarding the energy demands of desalination, the integration of RO technology with renewable energy sources, specially Photovoltaic (PV) systems, presents an appealing solution (Filippini et al., 2019). This proposition is of particular significance in Almería, given the region’s substantial potential for PV generation (Gomez-Exposito et al., 2020). This approach not only helps to reduce the carbon footprint of RO plants but also lowers operational expenses while severing the connection between water prices and fluctuating fuel costs (Mito et al., 2019). Nonetheless, this synergy remains unrealized in the present, as the predominant source of energy for these facilities derives from conventional on-grid electricity, primarily fueled by fossil resources. Note that the utilization of sustainable renewable sources accounts for only around 1% of the total desalination facilities globally (Mehmood and Ren, 2021).

Actually, to assess the impact on the Operational Expenditures (OPEX) of the inclusion of PV generation in RO systems is a non-trivial endeavor. In scenarios where PV generation and the electrical grid coexist, numerous variables come into play, including the fluctuating electricity output of the PV system, considerations related to battery utilization, and the varied pricing structures of the electricity grid. Furthermore, it becomes imperative

to engage in demand-side management of the RO system to achieve cost minimization while preserving system reliability to meet the load requirements (Karavas et al., 2019). This complexity adds further intricacy to the assessment process. Despite this heterogeneous scenario, in much of the existing literature, OPEX are often calculated using fixed amounts (Caldera and Breyer, 2019), which fails to account for the aforementioned dynamic factors. This is because most times, stand-alone systems are analyzed (Es-fahani and Yoo, 2016; Freire-Gormaly and Bilton, 2019). However, in the aforementioned heterogeneous scenario, the development and incorporation of optimal energy management systems into economic models are essential, which is identified as a current research gap in this field.

One of the emerging optimal management strategies in the literature is the so-called Energy Hub (EH) paradigm (Geidl et al., 2006). This broad methodology allows one to build a model that represents energy and mass balances between certain input resources that can be converted into other output resources. Within this methodology, each component of the system is usually characterized by static or time-variant representative conversion factors. This technique has found recent application in systems involving desalination for control and scheduling purposes, as demonstrated in studies such as (Sani et al., 2019), where EH was utilized to fulfill the electricity, heat, and water demands of a cement plant, or in (Jalili et al., 2021), where EH was employed for optimal day-ahead operation of a microgrid based on a coastal energy hub. Nevertheless, what is particularly valuable for economic assessment is that EH permits scheduling over comprehensive representative time periods, such as entire years, while considering the dynamic factors integral to the operation of a specific system. In the context of desalination, this approach was previously introduced in the work by (Gil et al., 2021), where EH was employed to simulate OPEX costs over a one-year duration within a network comprising a thermal desalination plant, a solar thermal field, a biomass boiler, and an isolated greenhouse. However, in this first approach the EH was combined with rule-based control, without performing optimal scheduling of the network at hand.

Based on all the above, the main contribution of this work are three-fold:

- First, an existing RO unit located in Almería is fully characterized for irrigation in greenhouse environments, thus overpassing the lack of particularization of current centralized desalination policies in the region.

- Second, different scenarios of combination between RO and PV are studied for the irrigation of such systems in order to address possible real-world implementations where renewable energy is considered.
- Third, a fully economic model based on the EH methodology to assess the cost of water and cash flow is presented, thus filling the gap for evaluating heterogeneous scenarios. The inclusion of EH provides a framework in which various aspects such as variable PV generation, electricity price, and water demand can be considered to accurately determine OPEX during representative operating years.

Moreover, all the work is based on the Agroconnect infrastructure (www.agroconnect.es), located at the IFAPA center adjacent to the University of Almería (Almería, Spain). This facility encompasses various components, including a representative greenhouse, water production via an RO system, and electricity generation through PV. Utilizing this infrastructure as a reference for acquiring experimental and economic data ensures that the findings derived from this study accurately mirror real-world practical scenarios.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the primary materials utilized in this study. This includes a description of the Agroconnect environment and the RO unit used. Furthermore, this section outlines the key methodologies employed for the experimental campaign, modeling, and the design of the economic model. Section 3 presents and discusses the main results concerning RO unit modeling, characterization, and economic assessment. Finally, the conclusions are summarized in Section 4.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Context of the research and material employed

2.1.1. Context

As mentioned, the research is centered around the Agroconnect environment. Agroconnect is a scientific-technological infrastructure project that received funding from the Ministry of Science, Innovation, and Universities in 2020. This test-bed, unique in the world, consists of a fully-equipped greenhouse of 1900 m², including electrical and thermal supply, heating and cooling systems, as well as water and CO₂ generation and reuse from renewable sources.

Focusing on water generation, the water grid (see Fig. 1) of Agroconnect environment includes two desalination systems to meet the demand for water

in the greenhouse. The first, and principal desalination strategy, is an RO unit with a nominal specific consumption of 3 kWh/m^3 , which is fed directly from a 100 m^3 seawater tank and can generate 11 m^3 of desalinated water per day. This water is stored in a 100 m^3 osmosis water tank. In addition, the RO unit can generate up to $22 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ of brine that is stored in a 50 m^3 tank and used to feed the Membrane Distillation (MD) system. This system is an MD unit capable of generating $6 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ of distillate water. The MD unit requires a continuous heat source for proper operation. To ensure its supply, there is a 160 kW biomass boiler, a thermal energy tank with a capacity of 4000 L , and a 30-panel solar thermal generation system. Regarding the electricity supply required by both the RO and MD units, there is a PV generation system made up of two units of 18 panels with a power generation capacity of 16.2 kW , together with two hybrid inverters and batteries with a capacity to store 44.2 kWh . It should be remarked that the connection to the electricity grid is also available.

Among the aforementioned systems, this study specifically concentrates on evaluating the RO facility's production and energy consumption under real operating conditions. The gathered data will be exclusively utilized for conducting an economic assessment related to greenhouse irrigation. The subsequent section is entirely dedicated to providing a comprehensive description of the RO system.

Figure 1: Agroconnect environment. (a) Aerial image of the facilities, and (b) schematic diagram of the water grid.

2.1.2. Reverse Osmosis facility's description

The RO system of Agroconnect (see Fig. 2) was designed and marketed by Elemental Water Makers. Figure 3 shows the schematic diagram of the whole system installed in Agroconnect, and Tab. 1 summarizes the main characteristics provided by the manufacturer. In addition, according to the system datasheet, the RO unit has a nominal water production of 11 m³ per day with a nominal specific consumption of 3 kWh/m³, operating with a feed at 25 °C and 32 g/L TDS salinity. Note that these figures align with the consumption and production data documented in the literature for RO systems incorporating energy recovery, as indicated by previous studies (Kim et al., 2019; Urrea et al., 2019). Moreover, in this RO module, the membranes are placed in spiral wound configuration, and it has a total membrane surface of 20.48 m².

Figure 2: RO system of Agroconnect.

The operation of the system can be explained through Fig. 3. First, the feed pump drives the feed water¹ to the first pre-treatment stage. This stage is made up of a sand filter in charge of eliminating most of the large particles that are in the water and that could damage the desalination plant.

¹The feed water is not taken directly from the sea, but from a well located very close to the sea, so the salinity is lower than the salinity of seawater.

Technical specifications	Minimum	Maximum
Flow (feed & flush) [m ³ /h]	1.37	-
Pressure (feed & flush) [bar]	0.5	5
TDS range, feed water [g/L]	1.5	45
Membrane pressure range [bar]	20	69
Feed water temperature [°C]	0.5	45
Ambient temperature [°C]	0.5	50
Maximum back pressure on fresh water [bar]	-	1

Table 1: Main characteristics of the RO system.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of the RO system.

After this stage, the water travels to the second stage of the pre-treatment, which consists of a set of cartridge filters. As can be seen in the Fig. 3, the first filter has a nominal filtering capacity of 5 microns while the second, an absolute capacity of 10 microns. Together, these cartridge filters ensure that particles larger than 5 microns are removed before entering the desalination unit. Next, the pre-treated water enters the RO unit, being pumped through the high pressure pump to the membranes. On the one hand, the osmosis water produced is circulated to the permeate water tank, which, in turn, is used to clean the system. This cleaning is performed through an integrated

automatic fresh water flush system, which operates at each start/stop, after 4 hours running, and after 24 hours stand-by. On the other hand, the brine discharge is driven to the brine storage available at Agroconnect facility.

The facility is fully monitored in terms of flow and pressure by using the devices reflected in Fig. 3. In addition, it includes a control system which automatically shuts-off the RO unit in case the salinity of the water produced exceeds 550 mg/L. Regarding electricity, the consumption of the system is registered continuously by means of a Schneider Electric's PowerTag system.

2.2. Methodologies employed in the research

2.2.1. Experimental methodology

The main objective of the experimental campaign is to characterize the influence on the RO system of the feed temperature, which varies naturally throughout the year, thus deviating from the nominal operating point provided by the manufacturer, and the feed pressure, which can be manually modified by the operator. In the case of salinity, no variations were contemplated since the feed water was used in the conditions that arrive at the Agroconnect facilities, conditions almost constant among 17-18 g/L TDS. Therefore, since the temperature variation of the feed depends on the temperature variation of the seawater, steady state experiments were conducted from December 2021 to October 2022 on days in which noticeable differences (ie, differences of more than 1 °C) in seawater temperature were observed. In particular, the temperature range covered was from 16.10 to 35.50 °C, trying to cover the range of temperatures included in the typical characteristics of seawater in the desalination report of the Spanish Ministry of Health and Social Policy (Sánchez et al., 2009), which is from 15 to 35 °C. Within this range, a total of 16 runs were performed. On each run, the system was operated at three different feed pressure settings, i.e., the three pressure setpoints that the feed pump allows the operator to set, which are 1, 1.5, and 3.6 bar. Consequently, a total of 48 samples were available to characterize the system.

Note that each steady-state experiment was performed in the following way: i) the first 20 minutes of the experiment were discarded to avoid the oscillations of the beginning of the operation, ii) after this time, three samples were taken for analysis, spaced at a time of 15 min between them, and iii) the recorded data was the average of these three samples. It should be remarked that the flow, pressure, and energy consumption data were consulted directly from the devices available in the facility, while parameters such as temperature and salinity were measured manually.

2.2.2. Key performance metrics for RO system characterization

Different metrics were used to evaluate the performance of the RO system. The first one is the permeate production which is denoted with variable F_P [m^3/h] and can be measured directly through the FT2 flow transmitter in the real plant, see Fig. 3.

The salt rejection factor (S_R) was considered as well in order to observe the quality of the water produced. This parameter can be calculated as:

$$S_R[\%] = 100 \cdot \frac{S_{\text{Feed}} - S_P}{S_{\text{Feed}}}, \quad (1)$$

where S_{Feed} is the salinity of the feed water [g/L], and S_P is the salinity of the osmosis water produced [g/L].

The Recovery Ratio (RR), which indicates the conversion of the system, i.e., the percentage of permeate obtained from a given feed flow rate, was also studied. This factor can be computed as follows:

$$\text{RR}[\%] = 100 \cdot \frac{F_P}{F_{\text{Feed}}}, \quad (2)$$

where F_{Feed} is the feed flow rate [m^3/h] measured from FT1 transmitter in the real facility, see Fig. 3.

Finally, the Specific Energy Consumption (SEC, [kWh/m^3]), which denotes the amount of electrical energy required to produce a unit of distillate, was employed to characterize the efficiency of the process:

$$\text{SEC}[\text{kWh}/\text{m}^3] = \frac{W_{\text{RO}}}{F_P}, \quad (3)$$

where W_{RO} denotes the electrical power [kW] required by the RO system.

2.2.3. Modeling methodology to characterize the RO system

To model the variables studied in this work, static surface polynomials functions were used due to the quasi-linear behaviour observed in the experimental data collected, as well as the ease that this type of models offer to be included in EH strategies. These kinds of models are a common choice in desalination systems (Khayet et al., 2011; Srivastava et al., 2021; Karunakaran et al., 2022), being specially appropriated when variations in feed salinity are not taken into account (as happened in this study) since this variable tends to induce non-linear behavior in the desalination systems (Khayet et al., 2011;

Gil et al., 2018). Therefore, taking nomenclature y to denote the output of the model, and $u_i \forall i \in 1, \dots, m$ to denote the inputs, being m the number of inputs, the polynomial equations can be written as follows:

$$y = w_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \cdot u_i + \sum_{i=1}^m w_{ii} \cdot u_i^2 + \sum_{1 \leq i < k}^m w_{ik} \cdot u_i \cdot u_k, \quad (4)$$

where w_0 is an offset coefficient (also known as bias), w_i are the coefficients of the linear terms, u_i and u_k are the input variables of the model, w_{ii} are the coefficients of the quadratic terms, w_{ik} are the coefficients of the interaction terms. Note that in this modelling methodology, the nonlinearity is only given by the quadratic terms, so it is valid to adjust linear and smooth nonlinear behaviours depending on the number of terms included in the equations.

To adjust the polynomial functions, the *fit* function of MATLAB (MATLAB, 2022) was used. Specifically, different polynomials were adjusted in each case, choosing the configuration that gave the best fit according to the criteria of coefficient of determination, R^2 , and Mean Square Error (MSE).

2.2.4. Determining operating costs: Energy Hubs paradigm

After the experimental evaluation, the idea is to use the obtained models for conducting an economic assessment of the system, considering both operational and investment costs. OPEX encompass expenses related to the operational needs of the system. Calculating OPEX in RO processes involves considering various factors, including expenses such as water pretreatment costs and the energy resources required by the system. For this specific study and taking into account the configuration of the Agroconnect facility, the following terms have been considered:

- Chemicals and other consumables (OPEX_{CH}): This cost includes the expenses related to the chemicals utilized in the RO process. According to existing literature, this cost can be quantified as a function of the volume of freshwater produced, typically ranging from 0.02 to 0.03 €/m³ (Papapetrou et al., 2017).
- Membrane replacement (OPEX_{MR}): A significant operating expense in RO processes is associated with membrane replacement. While the actual cost depends on the membrane's lifespan, typically around 5

years, it can be estimated annually as a fixed percentage, ranging from 5 to 20 %, of the initial membrane purchase cost per year, as reported in (Atikol and Aybar, 2005)

- Annual cost of maintenance, spares, and insurance ($OPEX_{MSI}$): This cost encompasses the annual cost of maintenance, spares, and insurance of the RO facility, which can be calculated as a fixed percentage, typically around 1-2 %, of the total capital cost, as mentioned in (Rahimi et al., 2021).
- Energy cost ($OPEX_E$): In the context of RO systems, calculating the electrical energy consumption depends on the SEC (see Eq. (3)) value and the volume of water produced. However, when considering scenarios that involve PV energy, converting this consumption into a cost becomes a challenging task. Hence, one of the noteworthy innovations in this study is the determination of the energy costs for the RO system using the EH paradigm, which will be introduced below.
- Operation and maintenance of the PV system ($OPEX_{PV}$): Finally, an operational and maintenance cost for the PV field has been incorporated, equating to 1 % of the total capital cost

Focusing on the term $OPEX_E$, the EH methodology represents a systematic approach for modeling and optimizing uncertain environments, particularly when diverse resources play a pivotal role (Ding et al., 2022). This is precisely the scenario addressed in this study, where achieving a realistic and representative $OPEX_E$ estimation necessitates the consideration of variables such as fluctuating electricity prices, renewable energy generation variations, and typical greenhouse water demands.

Consequently, the EH problem proposed here involves an optimization approach with the objective of minimizing the system’s energy costs while satisfying the greenhouse’s water requirements, which can be seen as a demand-side optimal strategy. In simpler terms, this methodology enables the calculation of the optimal energy operational costs of the RO system across a specified operational timeframe, which can encompass days, weeks, months, or even years. The EH methodology proposed is a matrix-based modelling framework based on energy and mass balances between a set of input resources (**I**) that can be transformed into another set of output resources (**O**). In this approach, various elements within the EH are defined as devices (**D**)

and storage systems (\mathbf{S}). These elements are associated with different parameters such as conversion ($\boldsymbol{\mu}$) or degradation factors ($\boldsymbol{\mu}_s$), among others. In particular, the case study proposed in this study contemplates water produced by the RO desalination unit (I_3) as the only source of water and two sources of electricity: the electrical grid (I_1) and a solar PV plant (I_2). In addition, electrical and water storage are also contemplated (S_1, S_2). The schematic diagram of the EH is depicted in Fig. 4, which actually follows the real configuration of Agroconnect environment.

Figure 4: EH Scenario. Inputs, outputs, and variables are described in Appendix A.

Based on this case study, three scenarios are contemplated in order to address various configurations and possible real-world implementations:

- **Scenario A:** No PV generation, i.e., the PV field contributes 0% of the electricity required by the RO system.
- **Scenario B:** Scenario in which the PV field accounts for approximately 50% of the electricity demand of the RO system.
- **Scenario C:** Scenario in which the PV field supplies approximately 95% of the RO system's demand.

To apply the EH scheduling paradigm to each case, the methodology introduced in (Ramos-Teodoro et al., 2020) is applied with slight modifications to characterize the case study at hand. The optimization problem of the EH methodology can be formulated as follows:

$$\text{OPEX}_E = \min \sum_{k=1}^H (\mathbf{c}(k) \mathbf{I}(k)), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{c}(k)$ is a vector containing the price for resources purchased, $\mathbf{I}(k)$ is a vector for the resource input flows, H is the prediction horizon, and k denotes a specific discrete-time instant (referred to an hourly basis for the problem at hand). This optimization problem is governed by various constraints related to the physical capacities of the systems, including operational flows and storage limits. These constraints can be seen in Appendix B (Eqs. B.1 – B.14); however, it is important to note the main differences from the constraints outlined in (Ramos-Teodoro et al., 2020). The first one relies on Eq. (B.13), which avoid energy flows in the opposite direction to that defined in the EH diagram (see Fig. 4). In this way, the results obtained are easier to interpret. Finally, consider Eq. (B.14) which is one of the most important constraints to make the scheduling optimization more representative with the real-world facility. Normally, one output (O_i), can be satisfied indifferently by an input (I_i) or by a storage device (S_i). In this case, the greenhouse water demand (O_2) must be fulfilled directly and exclusively from the water storage tank (S_2) as this is how real plant is working. Regarding the parameters used in the simulations, Tab. A.13 shows the values of the degradation, conversion, and loading and unloading coefficients of the systems. Meanwhile, Tab. A.14 shows the limits of the continuous decision variables.

2.2.5. Economic Indicators: Levelized cost of water and net present value

For the economic evaluation of the system, two different metrics have been used, the Levelized Cost of Water (LCOW) and the Net Present Value (NPV). On the one hand, the LCOW is a metric that evaluates the price at which water must be sold to achieve breakeven for a project. This calculation involves dividing the discounted project costs over its lifetime by the discounted volume of water produced during the same period. Utilizing this metric facilitates the comparison of the relative feasibility of various technologies, plant layouts, sizes, and other factors. The LCOW can be calculated as follows (Colciaghi et al., 2022):

$$\text{LCOW} = \frac{\text{CAPEX} + \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{\text{OPEX}}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^N \frac{W_p}{(1+i)^t}}, \quad (6)$$

where OPEX is the total operating costs per year [€], CAPEX is the total capital cost [€], W_p is the total water production per year [m³], N is the project time life, and i the discount rate. Please note that the CAPEX, for the facility at hand, can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{CAPEX} = \text{CAPEX}_{\text{RO}} + \text{CAPEX}_{\text{PV}}, \quad (7)$$

where CAPEX_{RO} [€] encompasses the expenses associated with the RO system, its installation, and the water storage tank, and CAPEX_{PV} [€] covers the costs of the PV system, batteries, inverters, and the installation of the entire system. These cost figures have been derived from the actual expenses of the Agroconnect system.

On the other hand, a cash flow analysis utilizing the NPV index has also been conducted to offer insights into what the investment and operation of the RO system under study can signify for farmers. This metric is given by:

$$\text{NPV}(n) = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{R_T - \text{OPEX}_{\text{GH}}}{(1+i)^t} - \text{CAPEX}, \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \quad (8)$$

where R_T [€] is the total revenues per year and OPEX_{GH} [€] is the total operating cost of the greenhouse (labour, seeds, fertilizers, or electricity,) including the OPEX of the RO system reported in Section 2.2.4, whereas n denotes the year under study. Please note that CAPEX solely encompasses the capital cost of the RO and PV systems, according to Eq. (7). The expenses related to the greenhouse structure itself will not be taken into account, as the intention is to exclusively assess the RO system and PV field.

3. Results

This section presents the main results obtained, starting from the experimental data and modeling of the RO unit, and finishing by the economical study encompassing both operational and investment costs, along with the final determination of the LCOW and NPV for the studied cases.

3.1. RO unit characterization

3.1.1. Experimental data

The data obtained from the experimental campaign are presented in Fig. 5. Moreover, Tab. 2 summarizes the operating range of each of the

variables involved in the study. It should be remarked that in all runs, the feed salinity only varied between 17.30 and 18.10 g/L TDS, so it was considered constant. Also, the feed flow rate was constant in all the experiments at 1.3 m³/h.

Figure 5: Experimental data. Effect of the feed temperature (T_{Feed}) and pressure (P_{Feed}) in (a) permeate production (F_P), (b) specific energy consumption (SEC), (c) salt rejection factor (S_R), and (d) recovery ratio (RR).

Variable	Nomenclature	Range
Feed temperature [°C]	T_{Feed}	16.1 - 35.5
Feed pressure [bar]	P_{Feed}	1 - 3.7
Permeate production [m ³ /h]	F_P	0.47 - 0.5
Specific energy consumption [kWh/m ³]	SEC	2.55 - 3.44
Salt rejection factor [%]	S_R	98.10 - 99.18
Recovery ratio [%]	RR	34.97 - 38.53

Table 2: Range of the experimental data.

By visualizing the obtained data, and focusing on the salt rejection plot

(Fig. 5-(c)), it can be observed how the quality of the permeate was practically constant regardless the operating conditions. This was to be expected, since this parameter is mainly affected when the feed salinity is altered, as shown in the experimental data reported in (Khayet et al., 2011). Consequently, it will not be included in the model developed in the following section.

With respect to the rest of the parameters studied (see Figs. 5-(a), (b), (d)), the influence of the feed temperature and pressure is almost linear in all of them. Namely, the higher the feed pressure, the higher the permeate production and RR, and the higher the SEC. Conversely, the higher the feed temperature, the lower permeate production, RR, and SEC. This quasi-linear trend justifies the fit of the experimental data through low-order surface polynomial models, as shown in the following section.

3.1.2. RO system model

As mentioned, each of the outputs y , i.e., permeate production, RR, and SEC, were modeled through polynomial surface functions that depend on feed temperature and pressure. Therefore, and following Eq. (4), the polynomial functions can be described as follows:

$$y = w_0 + w_1 \cdot T_{\text{Feed}} + w_2 \cdot P_{\text{Feed}} + w_{11} \cdot T_{\text{Feed}}^2 + w_{22} \cdot P_{\text{Feed}}^2 + w_{12} \cdot T_{\text{Feed}} \cdot P_{\text{Feed}}. \quad (9)$$

After carrying out the experimental campaign, the data collected were used to determine the weights of Eq. (9) for each of the outputs, according to the methodology reported in Section 2.2.3. The weights that provided the best fit are listed in Tab. 3. Moreover, Tab. 4 depicts the value of coefficient of determination (R^2) and MSE for each case, as well as the maximum error committed by the model. As observed, in all cases, the coefficient of determination took a value close to 0.9 or higher, indicating a good fit. Similarly, both the MSE and maximum error were close to zero in all cases, confirming the goodness of the model.

Apart from the quantitative results, Fig. 6 shows the comparison between the observed values and the provided values by the models. As can be seen, all the surfaces agree well with the experimental data. In addition, these surfaces serve to visualize more clearly the aforementioned quasi-linear behavior exhibited by all outputs. It can be seen how the increase in pressure improves the production metric and, therefore, the recovery ratio, but at the cost of

Polynomial weight	Outputs		
	F _p	SEC	RR
w_0	0.4884	3.832	37.52
w_1	-0.000443	-0.0769	-0.02966
w_2	0.006913	0.1131	0.5314
w_{11}	-	0.001015	$-8.903 \cdot 10^{-5}$
w_{12}	$3.724 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.0009279	0.002892
w_{22}	-0.001068	0.009584	-0.08218

Table 3: Values of the polynomial weights to each of the outputs considered.

Metric	Outputs		
	F _p	SEC	RR
R ²	0.8966	0.9720	0.8967
MSE	$1.5490 \cdot 10^{-6}$ [m ³ /h]	0.0018 [kWh/m ³]	0.0092 [%]
Maximum error	0.0033 [m ³ /h]	0.1373 [kWh/m ³]	0.2518 [%]

Table 4: Goodness of the adjustment of the obtained models.

higher energy consumption. On the contrary, the increase in temperature negatively affects the production of the system and the SEC.

3.2. Operating costs determination

Once the model of the RO system was developed, the next step was to determine the annual operating costs for the three scenarios outlined in Section 2.2.4. On first place, the term $OPEX_E$ was optimally calculated through the EH methodology by using as reference the model obtained for the RO system. To do that, the scheme presented in Fig. 7 was followed, with the data and model defined as follows:

- Greenhouse water consumption was calculated using the validated model presented in (Rodríguez et al., 2015), which allowed us to obtain the water demand of the Agroconnect greenhouse crop for one year on an hourly basis, see Fig. 8. Please note that the model was configured as detailed in (Gil et al., 2021) using tomato crop, and considering a unique long growing season from September to the end of June. In addition, a crop surface area of 2600 m² was considered in order to balance the demand of the greenhouse with the RO module characterized

Figure 6: Comparison between predicted values by the obtained models and experimental data. (a) Permeate production (F_P), (b) specific energy consumption (SEC), and (c) recovery ratio (RR).

in the actual Agroconnect facility. It should be remarked that the output of this model is the water demand of the greenhouse on an hourly basis, which gives rise to the diary demand presented in Fig. 8-(c).

- The mean seawater temperature was obtained from (World sea temperature, 2023). The selected location was Almería (Spain) and the collected data (see Fig. 8 - (b)) was derived from several years of historical sea surface temperature data from daily satellite readings provided by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). Note that this data was on a monthly basis; hence, the temperature was assumed to be constant during each month.
- Global irradiation at 30° tilted was the data used for simulations. These data were obtained from the photovoltaic geographical information system (PVGIS) tool (European Commission, 2023). The database used was PVGIS SARA2, which contains Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) data from 2005 to 2020. The selected location was the IFAPA

Figure 7: Simulation scheme for the EH problem.

Figure 8: Inputs for annual simulations at IFAPA center. (a) Monthly mean global irradiation tilted at 30 ° C, (b) monthly mean seawater temperature, and (c) daily greenhouse water consumption.

center in La Cañada, Almería (36.8334, -2.402), and the data used are shown in Fig. 8-(a).

- For the EH model, in both scenarios, the values for O_3 were calculated using the polynomial function shown in Eq. (9), with the weights presented in Tab. 3 for the SEC and F_P case, as follows:

$$O_1 = F_P \cdot \text{SEC}. \quad (10)$$

- Also, the values for $\mu_{D,2}$ were calculated using the polynomial function shown in Eq. (9), with the weights presented in Tab. 3, but, in this case, considering the RR:

$$\mu_{D,2} = \frac{\text{RR}}{100}. \quad (11)$$

- The cost of electricity $c_1(k)$ was calculated according to the tariff of a local company by periods, as shown in the Tab. 5. Moreover, for PV energy and seawater no cost was considered, resulting in $c_2(k) = 0$ and $c_3(k) = 0$ (see Appendix A).

Period	Price [€/kWh]
Weekdays from 22:00 to 08:00 and weekends	0.2065
from 08:00 to 10:00 and 14:00 to 18:00	0.2483
from 10:00 to 14:00 and 18:00 to 22:00	0.3115

Table 5: Local company electricity tariff (Endesa SA).

Please, take into account that, considering the equations outlined in Section 3.1.2, both Eqs. (10) and (11) are influenced by the feed temperature and the operating pressure of the RO unit. In this regard, actual sea temperature data were incorporated into the simulation as previously commented, effectively imposing the variable T_{Feed} during optimization. In the case of the pressure, all simulations were carried out using the maximum operating pressure of the RO unit. This choice is based on the premise of evaluating the system under the most challenging energy consumption operating conditions (worst-case scenario), leading to higher operating costs. Finally, it is worth mentioning that in order to characterize the three scenarios discussed in Section 2.2.4, the number of PV panels integrated into the PV field was modified

in each case to achieve the specified percentages of electricity supply. Note that the effective area of each photovoltaic panel is 1.96 m^2 , so Scenario A, B, and C use 0, 3, and 8 PV panels, respectively, resulting in the total surface area specified in Tab. 6. The main results in terms of OPEX_E are presented also in Tab. 6, which, in addition, depicts the amount of electricity provided by the grid and PV system in each scenario.

Finally, it should be remarked that the different simulations were carried out using the solver Gurobi (2023) in MATLAB[®] on an AMD Ryzen 5 5600H 3.3 GHz CPU, taking approximately 3100 seconds on average for each yearly simulation. Note that there were no significant differences in the annual simulation times for each of the scenarios.

		Greenhouse area [m²]			2600
		Annual greenhouse water demand [m³]			1065.5
		Annual RO electric demand [kWh]			3920.4
Scenario	PV panels area [m²]	Grid electricity [kWh]	PV electricity [kWh]	OPEX_E [€]	
A	0	3920.4 (100 %)	0 (0 %)	804.87	
B	5.88	2107.22 (53.75 %)	1813.18 (46.25 %)	497.35	
C	15.68	237.58 (6.06 %)	3682.82 (93.94 %)	71.82	

Table 6: Annual simulations for each scenario considered.

As mentioned above, the greenhouse surface area considered for the case study was 2600 m^2 , which necessitated a total of 1065.5 m^3 of water per year for irrigation, leading to an energy consumption of 3920 kWh by the RO unit. Using this framework as reference, it can be observed that the percentage of electricity demand supplied by the PV system was approximately 0, 50, and 95% for scenarios A, B, and C, respectively. Under this distribution, the energy-related operating costs (OPEX_E) for scenario, A, B, and C, amounted to 804.87, 407.35, and 71.82 €, respectively. This reaffirms that OPEX experience a substantial reduction as the capacity of the PV field increases, as expected.

In order to exemplify the EH model proposed in this work and analyze its behavior in terms of water and electricity flows, two three-day and one-month long simulations were carried out considering scenario C, which represent a major challenge in the electricity energy scheduling and management. The results obtained in the case of the three-day-long simulation are presented

in Fig. 9. Note that, in the case of the electric power flows (Fig. 9-(a)), O_1 represents the electrical demand of the RO unit, which can be satisfied by electrical energy from the grid (I_1), electrical energy coming directly from the solar panels (I_2) or from the batteries (Q_1). Regarding the water flows (Fig. 9-(b)), the osmotized water demand O_2 can only be satisfied by the water discharge flow Q_2 . It is worth noting that I_3 represents the osmotized water generated by the RO and stored in S_2 . Note that, at the end of the simulation, the electricity stored in the batteries (S_1) is nearly zero, so the PV system was not oversized.

Concerning water flow rates, most of the time, greenhouse water demand (O_2) coincided with the periods of highest radiation, i.e., water demand is aligned with PV system production, so the activation profile of the RO unit coincides almost entirely with the photovoltaic power generation profile. This fact not only helps reduce electricity losses linked to battery usage but also minimizes the power grid's electrical consumption, consequently lowering operating costs associated with grid electricity.

Regarding the monthly simulation, the results are presented in Fig. 10. The water generated by the RO system maintained a constant profile throughout the month, except at specific times when the greenhouse water demand was reduced (see Fig. 10-(b)). On the other hand, the water tank accumulated a maximum of 12 m^3 of the 100 m^3 available. Regarding the electrical flows (Fig. 10-(a)), it can be observed that the energy accumulated in the battery was reduced to zero on most days. However, in the last days, due to a lower water demand the energy stored in the batteries increased. Thus, it can be seen that the number of panels for scenario C in this example allowed the supply of electricity on most days. Only in a few days in the middle of the month, the use of electricity from the grid was required, and there was an excess of PV energy in the last three days. These results are reasonable and logical within the configuration and operation of the system.

After determining $OPEX_E$, the total operating costs of the RO system could be calculated for each scenario, taking into account all the costs outlined in Section 2.2.4. The results are presented in Tab. 7. These figures were computed using the following tuning parameters for the economic model:

- $OPEX_{CH}$: 0.03 €/m^3 .
- $OPEX_{MR}$: 3% of the capital cost of the RO system.
- $OPEX_{MSI}$: 1% of the capital cost of the RO system.

Figure 9: Three days simulation for scenario C. (a) Electric power, and (b) water flows.

- $OPEX_{PV}$: 1% of the capital cost of the PV system.

Please note that all these tuning parameters align with values found in the existing literature, as detailed in Section 2.2.4. The only adjustment made was to the $OPEX_{MR}$ term. This adjustment was necessary because the

Figure 10: Monthly simulation for scenario C. (a) Electric power, and (b) water flows.

CAPEX figures reported in Tab. 8 encompass not only the RO module but also installation, hydraulic connections, and storage tank costs. As a result, the percentage was slightly reduced.

As observed, in scenario A, the electricity cost constituted the most substantial expense, accounting for 49.36% of the total OPEX. In scenarios B

Annual operating costs [€]	Scenario A	Scenario B	Scenario C
OPEX _{CH}	35.59 (2.18%)	35.59 (2.63%)	35.59 (3.65%)
OPEX _{MR}	592.41 (36.33%)	592.41 (43.84%)	592.41 (60.89%)
OPEX _{MSI}	197.47 (12.11%)	197.47 (14.61%)	197.47 (20.29%)
OPEX _E	804.87 (49.36%)	497.35 (36.80%)	71.82 (7.38%)
OPEX _{PV}	-	28.32 (2.09%)	75.53 (7.76%)
OPEX	1630.34	1351.14	972.82

Table 7: Annual operating costs of the RO unit in each scenario. The percentage signifies the proportion of the overall operating cost that each of the terms represents.

and C, the proportion of OPEX attributed to electricity was considerably reduced thanks to the use of the PV field, amounting to 36.80 and 7.38% of the total, respectively. In these scenarios, the predominant component of the operating expenses was membrane replacement.

3.3. Economic evaluation

After determining the operational cost of the system, this section presents a study on LCOW and cash flow (based on the NPV metric) with the aim of assessing the economic viability of the installation.

3.3.1. Levelized cost of water

The initial economic indicator under examination was the LCOW, with the objective of estimating the cost of water within each of the scenarios under investigation. To achieve this, Eq.(6) was employed, calculating the CAPEX as outlined in Eq.(7) with the data provided in Tab. 8. However, it should be noted that for characterizing each scenario based on the configuration of the PV field, the CAPEX_{PV} for scenario A was set at 0 €, while the CAPEX for scenarios B and C was determined through linear interpolation based on the number of panels (see Tab. 6) incorporated in each case, using the figures provided in Tab. 8. This resulted in CAPEX values of 2832 and 7553 €, for scenario B and C, respectively. Specifically, the distribution of CAPEX used in each scenario for the calculation of LCOW are presented in Tab. 9. Note that, by taking into account the time life of the system, which is assumed to be $N = 20$ following the figures used in (Rahimi et al., 2021; Colciaghi et al., 2022), the annualized cost of the system for each scenario can be calculated as well. These costs are computed by dividing CAPEX by

life time and adding the OPEX for each case, thus merging both OPEX and CAPEX. The annualized cost are also presented in Tab. 9.

Device	Capital cost [€]
RO unit	19747
PV field (36 panels)	33989

Table 8: Investment cost of the study devices. For the RO unit, this cost covers the acquisition of the RO unit, the storage tank, and their installation, which includes hydraulic connections. In the case of the PV system, the cost encompasses panels, batteries, inverters, and the installation of all associated equipment. These costs were obtained from real invoices of Agroconnect system.

Capital cost [€]	Scenario A	Scenario B	Scenario C
CAPEX _{RO}	19747 (100%)	19747 (87.46%)	19747 (72.34%)
CAPEX _{PV}	0 (0%)	2832 (12.54%)	7553 (27.66%)
CAPEX	19747	22579	27300
Annualized cost [€]	2617.69	2480.10	2342.82

Table 9: Capital costs in each scenario. The percentage signifies the proportion of the overall capital cost that each of the terms represents. Moreover, annualized cost is the annualized merged cost taking into account both CAPEX and OPEX.

Since the calculation of the LCOW depends on the discount rate factor, three different values of this factor, namely, 3, 5 and 10%, were employed in order to analyze its impact. These values were obtained from (Papapetrou et al., 2017) and represent the minimum and maximum values documented for European countries. Conversely, the time life of the facility was maintained fixed at $N = 20$, as commented before. The results obtained are presented in Fig. 11.

As can be seen, for low values of the discount factor (i.e., 3 and 5%), the highest LCOW was observed in scenario A (without PV generation), amounting to 2.65 and 2.87 €/m³, for a discount rate of 3 and 5%, respectively. However, this pattern underwent a significant shift for higher discount factor values (i.e., 10%), where the highest LCOW was obtained for scenario C, reaching a value of 3.69 €/m³. Focusing on scenario B and C, it can be observed that for a discount rate of 3%, the LCOW of scenario C was lower, accounting to 2.51 €/m³. However, as the discount rate increased,

Figure 11: LCOW value for each scenario depending on the choice of the discount factor.

the LCOW of scenario B became lower, reaching 2.83 and 3.54 €/m³ for a discount rate of 5 and 10%, respectively.

On the whole, as the discount factor increases, the decrease in OPEX resulting from the inclusion of electricity generation through PV becomes less significant, and scenario A takes precedence due to its lower initial CAPEX investment.

3.3.2. Cash flow analysis based on the net present value

Finally, in order to quantify the impact of the investment on the typical cash flow of a greenhouse environment, a cash flow analysis utilizing the NPV metric was conducted. To do that, the following assumptions were contemplated:

- The CAPEX considered in the analysis pertain solely to the RO-PV system, see Tab. 9. The CAPEX of the greenhouse itself was not factored in, as it constitutes a fixed expense independent of the desalination system.
- In relation to OPEX, the OPEX values reported in Tab. 7 for each scenario, attributable to the desalination system, were supplemented

with the standard operating costs associated with a greenhouse in the province of Almería, which are presented in Tab. 10. This combination yielded the term $OPEX_{GH}$ in Eq. (8). Note that since the CAPEX of the greenhouse was not taken into account, amortization costs were not added in $OPEX_{GH}$ as well.

- To quantify the revenues, i.e., the term R_T in Eq. (8), a crop yield of 16 kg/m^2 was employed, representing the nominal yield specified by the seedbed for the tomato crop under consideration. Besides, a tomato sales price between 0.65 and 0.91 €/kg was taken into account, representing the minimum and maximum prices observed during the 2021-2022 growing campaigns in Almería, as reported in (Cajamar, 2022).

Annual Operating Cost [€/ha]	
Labour	28900
Seeds	5900
Fertilizers	3900
Phytosanitary	3700
Electricity	1284
Transport	1900
Others	1700
Total [€]	47284

Table 10: Annual operating cost of the greenhouse, obtained from (Cajamar, 2022). Total refers to the total OPEX cost of the greenhouse under study, with a crop surface area of 2600 m^2 .

In addition to the previous considerations, it should be mentioned that a time life of 20 years was considered in Eq. (8), in line with the LCOW study performed in the previous section. Furthermore, a fixed discount rate of 10% was applied to assess the worst-case scenario. The obtained results are presented in Fig. 12.

By visualizing the results, it can be observed how, in all the scenarios, and considering the different tomato sales prices, the investment could be recovered in less than three years. Nevertheless, noteworthy differences between the cases were evident. For instance, when comparing scenario A with scenarios B and C, especially at the lowest tomato sales price, scenario A

Figure 12: NPV for each scenario and for different tomato sales prices.

stands out by recovering the investment within the first two years. In contrast, scenarios B and C had longer recovery times, recovering the investment in the second and second-and-a-half years, respectively. This trend persisted with higher tomato sales prices, naturally resulting in shorter recovery times across all scenario.

Moreover, when analyzing the NPV value in year 20, considering also the lowest tomato sales price, the values for scenario A, B, and C were 90233.9, 89778.5, and 88278.7 €, respectively. These figures confirm that the additional investment involved in acquiring the PV field penalizes cash flow, despite the fact that OPEX are significantly reduced. Nevertheless, the disparity between scenarios is relatively small, indicating that the investment in a PV field does not notably compromise the cash flow dynamics.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, a techno-economic analysis was conducted to evaluate the use of RO desalinated water for greenhouse irrigation in Almería (Spain), a region renowned for its vast concentration of greenhouses and solar energy potential. For this reason, three scenarios were studied: scenario A, where the RO module relied on the electrical grid; scenario B, with a PV field supplying approximately 50% of the RO module’s power needs; and scenario C, where the PV field nearly entirely covered the RO module’s energy requirements. To characterize these scenarios, an experimental campaign was carried out at the Agroconnect facility, involving detailed modeling of an existing RO module. The developed model served as the reference for studying the optimal system OPEX through the EH methodology, taking into account the configuration of each scenario, alongside variable electricity prices and greenhouse water demands. These operational costs were then integrated into an economic model to assess the cost of water and cash flow for each scenario under study. From the results obtained, the following conclusion can be drawn:

- The studied RO module displayed adequate performance for irrigation purposes, maintaining high permeate quality (with a salt rejection factor of around 99%) even when subjected to varying operating conditions influenced by location-specific factors, like sea temperature, and adjustable operational pressures set by the operator.
- In frameworks as the one studied in this work where the RO module was directly fed with seawater (without notable variations in feed salinity), its performance exhibited an almost linear behavior. Thus, metrics as permeate production, RR, and SEC could be modeled through polynomial functions obtaining coefficient of determination with values close to 0.9 (or higher), and MSEs close to zero. The obtained models evidenced how the higher the feed temperature, the lower permeate production, RR, and SEC, which leads, among other factors, to higher energy consumption in winter months and lower production during the summer months.
- Calculating OPEX becomes challenging when PV generation and the electrical grid coexist, in addition to fluctuating water demands. Consequently, the implementation of methodologies like EH becomes imperative for realistic OPEX assessment. Employing this methodology

revealed that in scenario A, electricity costs constituted the largest expenditure, comprising 49.36% of the total OPEX. In scenarios B and C, the proportion of OPEX attributed to electricity markedly decreased due to the integration of the PV field, accounting for 36.80% and 7.38% of the total, respectively. Furthermore, the study carried out using the EH methodology shows how the greenhouse water demand and PV production are aligned, which indicates a great potential for harnessing the energy generated by the PV system in the application under study.

- LCOW values between 2.51 and 3.69 €/m³ were obtained for the different scenarios and taking into account different discount factor values. The analysis performed revealed a great dependence of the LCOW value on the discount factor. At lower discount factor values, scenarios incorporating PV demonstrated a lower LCOW. However, as the discount factor increased, the reduction in OPEX achieved by integrating PV electricity generation became less pronounced. Consequently, scenario A, characterized by its lower initial CAPEX, obtained lower LCOW values.
- Finally, the cash flow analysis demonstrates that the investment in RO systems for greenhouse irrigation can be recovered in less than three years across all scenarios. These findings suggest that utilizing RO systems for greenhouse irrigation is a viable investment option with a relatively quick return on investment. This could be particularly appealing to individual farmers or small associations in specific districts, thereby promoting the adoption of a distributed desalination system. Moreover, the relatively minor differences observed between scenarios indicate that incorporating a PV field alongside the RO system does not significantly disrupt cash flow dynamics, indicating good potential for this combination, especially if the current tariff policy of the power grid increases, and the investment price of the PV system decreases.

Future work will focus on studying how economies of scale can influence these applications. Additionally, diverse alternatives for treating system waste, specifically brine, will undergo evaluation. This assessment will encompass exploring the potential utilization of the MD system included in the Agroconnect environment.

Appendix A. Model variables and parameters

Appendix A.1. Variable definition

It is important to note that the optimization problem involves two types of variables. The first type can be deterministically computed using methodologies outlined in the existing literature. The second type represents the decision variables of the optimization problem, and as such its value is not known a priori. Consequently, in Tab. A.11, the “Value” column specifies the sources of information or the calculation methodology for the values associated with the first class of variables. In contrast, the decision variables do not have an associated value in that column, since the value is decided by the solver.

Variable	Description	Units	Value
I_1	Grid electricity	kW	-
I_2	Sun radiant power	kW	(European Commission, 2023)
I_3	Seawater for RO unit	m ³ /h	-
D_1	Photovoltaic modules	-	-
D_2	RO unit	-	-
O_1	Electricity for RO unit	kW	$F_p \cdot \text{SEC}$ (See Eq. (3))
O_2	Greenhouse water demand	m ³ /h	(Rodríguez et al., 2015)
S_1	Electricity storage	kWh	-
S_2	Osmotized water storage	m ³ /h	-

Table A.11: Input, devices, output and storage variables description.

P_p	Path
P_1	$I_1 \rightarrow O_1$
P_2	$I_2 \rightarrow D_1 \rightarrow O_1$
P_3	$I_3 \rightarrow D_2 \rightarrow O_2$

Table A.12: Vector \mathbf{P} elements for each path in the real plant.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{O}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} O_1(\mathbf{k}) \\ O_2(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{I}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} I_1(\mathbf{k}) \\ I_2(\mathbf{k}) \\ I_3(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, \\
\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} P_1(\mathbf{k}) \\ P_2(\mathbf{k}) \\ P_3(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mu_{D,1}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mu_{D,2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, \\
\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} S_1(\mathbf{k}) \\ S_2(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{Q}_{\text{ch}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} Q_{\text{ch},1}(\mathbf{k}) \\ Q_{\text{ch},2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, \\
\mathbf{Q}_{\text{dis}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} Q_{\text{dis},1}(\mathbf{k}) \\ Q_{\text{dis},2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{C}_{\text{s}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{S,1}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_{S,2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, \\
\mathbf{C}_{\text{ch}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{\text{ch},1}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_{\text{ch},2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{C}_{\text{dis}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{\text{dis},1}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_{\text{dis},2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, \\
\mathbf{C}_{\text{i}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{C}_{\text{di}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \\
\mathbf{C}_{\text{do}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mu_{D,1}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mu_{D,2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{D}_{\text{i}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} D_{i,1}(\mathbf{k}) \\ D_{i,2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, \\
\mathbf{D}_{\text{o}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} D_{o,1}(\mathbf{k}) \\ D_{o,2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{k}) &= [c_1(\mathbf{k}) \quad c_2(\mathbf{k}) \quad c_3(\mathbf{k})].
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix A.1.1. Binary variables definition

$$\begin{aligned}
\boldsymbol{\delta}_{\mathbf{O}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{D,2}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, & \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\mathbf{I}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{I,1}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \delta_{I,2}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \delta_{I,3}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, \\
\boldsymbol{\delta}_{\text{ch}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{\text{ch},1}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 \\ 0 & \delta_{\text{ch},2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, & \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\text{dis}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{\text{dis},1}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 \\ 0 & \delta_{\text{dis},2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}, \\
\boldsymbol{\delta}_{\text{Di}}(\mathbf{k}) = \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\text{Do}}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{D,1}(\mathbf{k}) & 0 \\ 0 & \delta_{D,2}(\mathbf{k}) \end{bmatrix}.
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix A.1.2. Boundary variables definition

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{I}^{\min}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} I_1^{\min} \\ I_2^{\min} \\ I_3^{\min} \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{I}^{\max}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} I_1^{\max} \\ I_2^{\max} \\ I_3^{\max} \end{bmatrix}, \\
 \mathbf{D}_i^{\min}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} D_{i,1}^{\min} \\ D_{i,2}^{\min} \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{D}_i^{\max}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} D_{i,1}^{\max} \\ D_{i,2}^{\max} \end{bmatrix}, \\
 \mathbf{D}_o^{\min}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} D_{o,1}^{\min} \\ D_{o,2}^{\min} \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{D}_o^{\max}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} D_{o,1}^{\max} \\ D_{o,2}^{\max} \end{bmatrix}, \\
 \mathbf{Q}_{\text{ch}}^{\min}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} Q_{\text{ch},1}^{\min} \\ Q_{\text{ch},2}^{\min} \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{Q}_{\text{ch}}^{\max}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} Q_{\text{ch},1}^{\max} \\ Q_{\text{ch},2}^{\max} \end{bmatrix}, \\
 \mathbf{Q}_{\text{dis}}^{\min}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} Q_{\text{dis},1}^{\min} \\ Q_{\text{dis},2}^{\min} \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{Q}_{\text{dis}}^{\max}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} Q_{\text{dis},1}^{\max} \\ Q_{\text{dis},2}^{\max} \end{bmatrix}, \\
 \mathbf{S}^{\min}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} S_1^{\min} \\ S_2^{\min} \end{bmatrix}, & \mathbf{S}^{\max}(\mathbf{k}) &= \begin{bmatrix} S_1^{\max} \\ S_2^{\max} \end{bmatrix}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Appendix A.2. Parameter definition

Coefficient	Description	Value
$\mu_{D,1}$	Radiant power to electricity factor conversion	(Duffie and Beckman, 2013)
$\mu_{D,2}$	Sea water to osmotized water RO factor conversion	RR/100 (See Eq. (2))
$\mu_{S,1}$	S_1 storage degradation factor	0.98
$\mu_{S,2}$	S_2 storage degradation factor	1
$\mu_{\text{ch},1}$	S_1 storage charging efficiency factor	0.7
$\mu_{\text{ch},2}$	S_2 storage charging efficiency factor	1
$\mu_{\text{dis},1}$	S_1 storage discharging efficiency factor	0.8
$\mu_{\text{dis},2}$	S_2 storage discharging efficiency factor	1

Table A.13: Conversion, degradation, charge and discharge coefficients.

Variable	Min	Max
I_1	0 kW	∞
I_2	0 kW	∞
I_3	0 m ³ /h	1.33 m ³ /h
$D_{i,1}$	0 kW	I_2^{\max}
$D_{i,2}$	0 m ³ /h	I_3^{\max}
$D_{o,1}$	0 kW	14 kW
$D_{o,2}$	0 m ³ /h	0.5 m ³ /h
$Q_{ch,1}$	0 kWh	8.26 kWh
$Q_{ch,2}$	0 m ³ /h	$D_{o,2}^{\max}$
$Q_{dis,1}$	0 kWh	8.26 kWh
$Q_{dis,2}$	0 m ³ /h	10 m ³ /h
S_1	0 kWh	44.16 kWh
S_2	0 m ³ /h	100 m ³ /h

Table A.14: Upper and lower limits for converters, storage capacity, charge and discharge flows.

Appendix B. Problem constraints

Appendix B.1. Balance equations

Considering \mathbf{P} as a vector of paths between input flows and output flows as defined in Tab. A.12, Eq. (B.1) shows an energy balance between demand flows ($\delta_o(k)\mathbf{O}(k)$), transformed input flows ($\mathbf{C}(k)\mathbf{P}(k)$) and storage flows ($\mathbf{Q}_{ch}(k) + \mathbf{Q}_{dis}(k)$). Eq. (B.2) assumes a linear relationship in storage system dynamics. Their dynamic implies that the system's state changes in accordance with the quantity of resource that leaves (discharge process) or enters (charge process) each storage system. Finally, Eqs. (B.3) – (B.5) show the relationships between inputs and devices flows with the vector \mathbf{P} .

$$\delta_o(k)\mathbf{O}(k) = \mathbf{C}(k)\mathbf{P}(k) - \mathbf{Q}_{ch}(k) + \mathbf{Q}_{dis}(k), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\mathbf{S}(k+1) = \mathbf{C}_s(k)\mathbf{S}(k) + \mathbf{C}_{ch}(k)\mathbf{Q}_{ch}(k) - \mathbf{C}_{dis}(k)\mathbf{Q}_{dis}(k), \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$\mathbf{I}(k) = \mathbf{C}_i(k)\mathbf{P}(k), \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$\mathbf{D}_i(k) = \mathbf{C}_{di}(k)\mathbf{P}(k), \quad (\text{B.4})$$

$$\mathbf{D}_o(k) = \mathbf{C}_{do}(k)\mathbf{P}(k). \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Appendix B.2. Capacity constraints

Eqs. (B.6) – (B.11) ensure that the vectors take values according to the real-world capacities of each facility.

$$\delta_{\mathbf{I}}(k)\mathbf{I}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{I}(k) \leq \delta_{\mathbf{I}}(k)\mathbf{I}^{\max}, \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$\delta_{\mathbf{D}_i}(k)\mathbf{D}_i^{\min} \leq \mathbf{D}_i(k) \leq \delta_{\mathbf{D}_i}(k)\mathbf{D}_i^{\max}, \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$\delta_{\mathbf{D}_o}(k)\mathbf{D}_o^{\min} \leq \mathbf{D}_o(k) \leq \delta_{\mathbf{D}_o}(k)\mathbf{D}_o^{\max}, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$\delta_{\mathbf{Q}_{\text{ch}}}(k)\mathbf{Q}_{\text{ch}}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{Q}_{\text{ch}}(k) \leq \delta_{\mathbf{Q}_{\text{ch}}}(k)\mathbf{Q}_{\text{ch}}^{\max}, \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$\delta_{\mathbf{Q}_{\text{dis}}}(k)\mathbf{Q}_{\text{dis}}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{Q}_{\text{dis}}(k) \leq \delta_{\mathbf{Q}_{\text{dis}}}(k)\mathbf{Q}_{\text{dis}}^{\max}, \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$\mathbf{S}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{S}(k) \leq \mathbf{S}^{\max}. \quad (\text{B.11})$$

Appendix B.2.1. Other constraints

Eq. (B.12) prevents batteries from being charged and discharged at the same discrete time instant, Eq. (B.13) avoid energy flows in the opposite direction to the defined one, and Eq. (B.14) forces the water required for output O_2 to be obtained exclusively from storage S_2 .

$$\delta_{\text{ch},1}(k) + \delta_{\text{dis},1}(k) \leq 1, \quad (\text{B.12})$$

$$\mathbf{P}(k) \geq \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{B.13})$$

$$\mathbf{Q}_{\text{ch},2}(k) = \mu_{\text{D},2}(k)\mathbf{P}_3(k). \quad (\text{B.14})$$

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